

ISic2730

I.Sicily inscription 2730

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

greeting

Material

mosaic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG6043

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333217

1. [χ]αῖρε.

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644830

EDCS 64400339

PHI 333217

Bibliography

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